

Advanced Nanocomposite Materials for Enhanced Performance in Oil and Gas Operations – A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract- The oil and gas (O&G) industry increasingly requires advanced materials capable of withstanding harsh operating environments such as deepwater, ultra-deepwater, and high-temperature/high-pressure (HTHP) reservoirs. Fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites have already provided benefits in corrosion resistance, weight reduction, and fatigue performance, yet their broader adoption remains limited by challenges such as poor impact resistance and inadequate fire performance. Nanocomposites—polymers reinforced with nanoparticles, including clays, metal oxides, carbon nanotubes, and graphene—offer a pathway to overcoming these limitations. Even at low filler concentrations, they can deliver significant improvements in mechanical strength, thermal stability, fire resistance, and barrier properties, while also enabling new functionalities in drilling fluids, cementing, and enhanced oil recovery (EOR). This review examines the state of nanocomposite research in the O&G sector, evaluates their potential to enhance both structural and fluid applications, and discusses the technical, economic, and regulatory challenges that must be addressed to achieve commercial deployment.

Keywords – Nanocomposites, Oil and Gas Industry, Enhanced Oil Recovery, Drilling Fluids, Carbon Nanotubes, Polymer Matrix Composites, HTHP Applications, Nanotechnology, Well Cementing, Rheological Properties.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 21st century continues to witness an ever-growing demand for advanced materials with enhanced properties that surpass those currently available. This need is particularly pressing in the oil and gas (O&G) industry, where exploration and production activities are increasingly moving into more complex and challenging environments such as deep and ultra-deep water, as well as high-temperature, high-pressure (HTHP) reservoirs. These harsh conditions impose extreme stress on conventional tools, equipment, and materials, often pushing them beyond their mechanical, thermal, and chemical stability limits. Consequently, the industry requires technological innovations and novel materials to ensure the safe and economical satisfaction of rising global energy demands [1, 2, 3].

Fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are among the materials well-positioned to address some of these challenges. They are valued for their excellent strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios, superior corrosion resistance, and good fatigue performance, while also allowing a high degree of design flexibility. Despite these advantages, traditional composites are hindered by significant drawbacks, including

poor impact resistance, high manufacturing costs, and limited fire performance. These limitations have restricted their widespread adoption in critical O&G applications [4, 5, 6]. In response, growing attention has turned to nanocomposites, a new class of materials that leverage the principles of nanotechnology to overcome many of these shortcomings. Nanotechnology, operating at the 1–100 nm scale, enables the development of materials with unique properties that surpass the capabilities of conventional approaches. Nanocomposites, broadly defined as materials composed of two or more distinct phases with at least one component in the nanometre range, often involve the dispersion of

nanoparticles (NPs) within a polymeric matrix. This integration can significantly enhance the mechanical, electrical, and thermal behavior of the host material [1, 7].

The unique properties of nanoparticles, particularly their small size and high surface-area-to-volume ratio, play a pivotal role in these improvements. Even small amounts of nano-additives can drastically enhance the performance of polymer matrices while having minimal impact on cost and processability. These enhancements are observed across multiple fronts. For instance, nanocomposites frequently display increased mechanical strength, improved toughness, higher thermal

stability, and greater fire resistance. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), for example, possess tensile strengths ranging from 50 to 200 GPa and can substantially reinforce both thermoplastic and thermoset polymers [8, 9]. Furthermore, nanocomposites often exhibit reduced gas permeability and improved resistance to chemical degradation and corrosion, making them highly suitable for applications such as pipes, valves, seals, and protective coatings. The ability to chemically modify nanoparticles also introduces the possibility of tailoring materials with specific, application-driven functionalities, paving the way for the development of “smart” materials in the sector [10, 11].

This review explores these property enhancements and evaluates how they may create new opportunities for the adoption of polymer-based composites in the O&G industry. Particular emphasis is placed on the upstream sector, where nanotechnology is being extensively investigated for use in drilling fluids, cementing, well stimulation, and enhanced oil recovery (EOR). As the viability of deepwater and marginal field developments increasingly relies on cost reduction and improved operational efficiency, the integration of such materials could prove decisive [12–17]. Beyond upstream, opportunities are also emerging in the downstream sector,

including natural gas processing and oily wastewater treatment, where polymer nanocomposites are showing promise as membranes and adsorbents [18,19]. While many potential applications remain in the research and development stage, several successful field trials have already demonstrated the immense potential of nanotechnology to transform the oil and gas industry [20].

Polymer nanocomposites are advanced materials that have garnered considerable attention across various industries, including oil and gas, due to their unique and enhanced properties. Among the many materials under study, some of the most common are based on naturally occurring layered silicate clays. These nanocomposites are typically produced by incorporating nanoparticles, such as clay, into a polymeric matrix to improve mechanical, electrical, and thermal performance. The resulting polymer-reinforced nanoclays can exhibit different structural arrangements, which are broadly classified as layered particles, intercalated structures, and delaminated or exfoliated structures. While layered particles are not considered true nanocomposites, intercalated and especially exfoliated systems provide significant improvements. Exfoliated structures are particularly desirable, as their high degree of homogeneity allows for optimal enhancement of material properties [21, 22].

Beyond layered silicates, other classes of nanofillers, including nanofibers such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and whiskers, are also being extensively investigated [8, 9]. A wide variety of nanoparticles and polymer nanocomposites are currently under development for applications in the oil and gas industry. One of the most widely studied examples is silicon dioxide (SiO₂), which is frequently combined with polymers such as polyacrylamide (PAM) or hydrolyzed polyacrylamide (HPAM). Polymer-coated SiO₂ nanocomposites have demonstrated the ability to increase oil recovery by altering reservoir wettability [3, 16]. Table 1 presents the applications of nanoparticles for enhanced oil recovery (EOR), highlighting their effects on reservoir properties and improvements in oil recovery.

II. ADVANCES IN NANOCOMPOSITE TECHNOLOGY

Investigated NP/Nanocomposite	Improved Parameters	Key Findings & Notes
Silicon Dioxide (SiO ₂) / Nanosilica	Wettability alteration [23-25]; IFT reduction [26-35]; increased sweep efficiency [23, 24]; improved foam and emulsion stability [36-47]; reduced surfactant adsorption [23, 24, 36-39, 48-53]; improved mobility control [25, 43-45, 54, 55].	The most widely investigated NP for EOR [45, 56-58]. Can increase oil recovery by 41–66% [70]. Used in environmentally acceptable conformance sealants [25, 43-45, 59, 60].

Aluminium Oxide (Al ₂ O ₃)	Reduced oil viscosity [61, 62]; improved stability and rheology of injected water [61-64]; altered wettability [64, 65].	Often used with SiO ₂ for low salinity hot water injection [61, 62]. Can increase oil recovery [23, 29, 65, 66]. Is also used for asphaltene formation damage inhibition and to enhance the mobility of heavy oils [67].
Iron Oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	Altered wettability, IFT, permeability, and oil viscosity [23-25].	Negative oil recovery was observed in one sandpack study [23, 29, 68].
Titanium Dioxide (TiO ₂)	Improved stability and rheology of injected water [61, 62].	Can be combined with SiO ₂ and Al ₂ O ₃ to improve rheological properties [29, 61, 62, 68]. Can also change wettability and reduce IFT [69, 70].
Metal Oxides (ZnO, MgO, ZrO ₂ , SnO ₂ , NiO)	Altered wettability [23, 24]; reduced IFT and oil viscosity [23, 24].	A wide range of metal oxides have been shown to positively influence EOR parameters [23, 24]. NiO/SiO ₂ Janus nanoparticles are effective at low concentrations and reduce interfacial tension [23, 24, 71, 72].
Graphene & Derivatives (GO, Graphene QDs)	Reduced oil viscosity [63, 73-79]; altered wettability [76-79]; reduced IFT [76-79].	Graphene oxide (GO) can reduce oil viscosity and increase recovery [63, 73-75]. Nitrogen-doped Graphene Quantum Dots (N-GQDs) increased oil recovery by 14-18% [80].
Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs)	Reduced IFT [81-83]. Can be functionalised with polymers to enhance borehole stability at high temperatures [84-86].	Studied in combination with silica as a nanohybrid for EOR [81-83]. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) have been used in drilling fluids to improve lubricity, rheological properties, and filtration characteristics [36, 51, 87, 88]. They have also been used in nanocomposites for high- temperature, high-pressure sealing applications [89-94].
Polymer-Coated Nanocomposites (e.g., polymer-SiO ₂)	Improved mobility control; altered surface wettability; increased oil recovery (up to 21%) [25, 43, 44, 95, 96].	Enhances solubility, stability, and transport through porous media [25, 43-45, 54, 55]. Can also improve the stabilisation of foams and emulsions [25, 43, 44]. Polymer-coated silica nanoparticles were found to increase oil recovery by about 10% [95, 96], while another study using polymer-coated SiO ₂ reported an increase of up to 21% [36, 88, 95, 96].
Potassium Chloride/Silica/Xanthan Nanocomposite	Altered wettability to water-wet; reduced IFT and contact angle [97-101].	Resulted in an additional oil recovery of 17.05% of the Original Oil In Place (OOIP) at an optimal concentration of 1000 ppm [97-101]. This is considered an environmentally friendly nanomaterial [97, 98, 99, 101].
Nanocatalysts (Multi-metallic)	In-situ heavy oil upgrading by breaking carbon-sulfur bonds in asphaltenes, reducing viscosity and average molecular weight [102-125].	A promising, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly technology to produce higher quality oils that meet pipeline and refinery specifications [54, 102, 103, 104, 105, 107-125]. Nanocatalysts exhibit unique catalytic properties due to their high surface area-to-

		volume ratio [54, 102, 103, 104, 105, 107-125].
Cellulose Nanocrystals (CNCs) & Surface-functionalized nanocellulose	Conformance control; stability of oil-in-water emulsions; "green" chemical EOR [48, 49, 63, 73-75, 126-128].	Used for improving mobility control and water plugging [48, 49, 128]. Surface-functionalised nanocellulose has been shown to improve oil recovery through water flooding [128]. CNCs can be used to divert fluid in porous media [126-128].

Table 1. Applications of Nanoparticles for Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR).

Metal oxides represent another important group of fillers, with aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) being the most commonly explored, followed by titanium dioxide (TiO_2), iron oxide (Fe_2O_3), zinc oxide (ZnO), and magnesium oxide (MgO) [11, 20]. These metal oxides are often used either individually or in hybrid systems, such as SiO_2-TiO_2 nanocomposites, which exhibit improved thermal stability and rheological properties for high-temperature applications [14].

Carbon-based nanomaterials form another critical category, comprising CNTs, graphene, graphene oxide (GO), and

fullerenes. CNTs, in particular, have generated significant interest due to their unique ability to enhance the electrical behavior of polymer matrices [3].

Functionalised multi-walled carbon nanotubes (FMWCNTs) have been incorporated into drilling fluids to improve rheological performance and filtration properties

[13]. Table 2 outlines the applications of nanoparticles in drilling fluids, focusing on improvements in rheology, filtration, stability, and HPHT performance.

Investigated NP/Nanocomposite	Improved Parameters	Key Findings & Notes
Silicon Dioxide (SiO_2)	Improved rheology and hole cleaning [126, 129-134]; shale inhibition [94, 135-140]; mitigated pore pressure transmission [135, 136, 137, 141, 142]; improved wellbore stability by plugging pores [126, 129-132, 141-146].	Effective at low concentrations (e.g., 3%) [147-149].
Metal Oxides (Al_2O_3 , CuO , MgO , TiO_2 , ZnO , Fe_2O_3)	Improved rheology [50, 92, 135-137, 150-155], filtration [50, 150], lubricity [39, 51, 87, 88, 156], heat transfer, thermal and electrical conductivity [51, 87, 88, 135-137, 154, 155, 157, 158].	Fe_2O_3/Fe_3O_4 are excellent additives for HPHT conditions [73, 74, 132-135, 159-162]. CuO nanofluid is more resistant to HPHT than ZnO -based nanofluid [157, 158, 163, 164].
Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs/MWCNTs)	Improved rheology, wellbore stability, and filtration for HPHT applications [50, 84-86, 150]; enhanced lubricity 51, 87, 88, 163, 165, 166].	Can be functionalised or used in polymer nanocomposites for enhanced performance [84-86, 89-91, 163-166].
Graphene & Derivatives (e.g., Functionalised Nanoporous Graphene - FNPG)	Improved rheology, filtration, lubricity, and shale hydration inhibition [23, 126-129].	Led to more economical drilling operations in a field trial in Iran [64, 167-169].
Nanoclay	Improved filtration; reduced electrical resistivity [51, 87, 88, 171-173]; improved rheology for synthetic-based drilling fluids [126, 130, 173].	Effective for drilling deep oil wells [92, 151-153].
Nanopolymer	Improved filtration; wellbore strengthening [126, 130, 173].	-

Zinc Titanate (ZnTiO ₃)	Improved rheology, thermal stability, and filtration characteristics [90, 135-137, 174].	-
Cellulose Nanofibers (CNFs)	Enhanced rheology and filtration control [175-177].	A renewable, non-toxic alternative to synthetic polymers with superior thermal stability compared to xanthan gum [175-177].

Table 2: Applications of Nanoparticles in Drilling Fluids.

Likewise, polymer-based nanocomposites prepared through techniques such as in-situ polymerisation or melt blending have opened new pathways for tailored solutions. For example, nanocomposites of poly(methyl methacrylate) with graphene oxide (PMMA-GO) have been developed as efficient pour-point depressants for waxy crude oil [178], while hybrid systems such as potassium chloride/silicon dioxide/xanthan (KCl/SiO₂/Xanthan) have shown promise in enhanced oil recovery (EOR) operations [12]. Despite these advances, the development of effective polymer nanocomposites remains a persistent challenge. Chief among these is the difficulty of achieving uniform dispersion of nanoparticles within the polymer matrix, which is critical for transferring the unique properties of the filler to the final composite. Agglomeration is a common issue, as nanoparticles like SiO₂ tend to cluster over time, leading to unstable nanofluids with compromised rheological properties [3, 179]. Such aggregation not only diminishes performance but can also block pore throats within reservoirs, causing formation damage. Compatibility issues present another hurdle. Natural fibres and nanofillers are often hydrophilic, whereas many thermoplastic polymer matrices are hydrophobic. This mismatch results in poor interfacial bonding and weakens the mechanical performance of the composite, making surface treatments or chemical modifications necessary to improve adhesion [5, 6].

Harsh reservoir conditions further complicate performance, as high temperatures may degrade polymer chains and reduce the stability of drilling fluids, while high salinity environments can destabilise nanofluid dispersions [180]. To address these limitations, various optimisation strategies have been developed. Co-stabilisers such as TiO₂ have been employed to reduce the homoagglomeration of SiO₂ nanoparticles [181], while surfactants and dispersants are often added to improve stability under saline conditions [19]. Such approaches aim to produce nanocomposites with uniform particle dispersion and strong interfacial adhesion between the filler and the polymer matrix. The ultimate goal is to harness the full potential of nanocomposites to provide durable, high-performance materials capable of meeting the demanding requirements of oil and gas operations [7].

III. POLYMERIC LAYERED SILICATES NANOCOMPOSITE: FORMATION AND PROPERTIES

Polymeric layered silicates (PLS), a widely studied class of polymer nanocomposites, have attracted particular interest due to their natural abundance, low cost, and well-understood intercalation chemistry [182]. These materials are typically derived from nanoclays such as montmorillonite (MMT), which consist of stacked silicate layers. To transform such materials from simple particle-reinforced composites into high-performance nanocomposites, the silicate layers must be separated and dispersed throughout the polymer matrix. When this dispersion is achieved, the resulting nanocomposite exhibits a very large aspect ratio, typically in the range of 100 to 1000, which is key to its enhanced performance [183].

The formation of PLS nanocomposites relies on the migration of polymer chains into the interlayer galleries of the silicate, which forces the layers apart and induces swelling. Depending on the extent of polymer penetration, the structure of the resulting nanoclay-polymer system can adopt three distinct morphologies [184]. In the immiscible or layered particle configuration, the polymer fails to penetrate the galleries, leaving the filler poorly dispersed and preventing the formation of a true nanocomposite. In intercalated structures, the polymer chains enter the galleries, increasing the interlayer spacing and creating a more intimate mixture of polymer and clay. The most desirable outcome, however, is the exfoliated or delaminated morphology, in which the silicate layers are fully separated and randomly dispersed within the polymer

matrix. Exfoliation provides superior homogeneity and is widely recognised as essential for optimising the properties of PLS nanocomposites [7, 185]. Achieving exfoliation is a delicate and complex process, influenced by both chemical and processing factors. Research into epoxy resin systems offers valuable insights into these mechanisms [186].

Some studies suggest that the increasing polarity of the polymer during polymerisation acts as an indirect driving force for exfoliation [187], as the rise in molecular weight alters polymer-clay interactions. Other investigations point to the importance of intragallery polymerisation kinetics, noting that exfoliation is more likely when polymerisation within the clay

galleries occurs at a rate equal to or faster than that of the bulk matrix [188]. Processing conditions, such as higher cure temperatures that accelerate polymerisation, have also been shown to promote better exfoliation and more uniform nanostructures [189]. The incorporation of layered silicates at relatively low additive levels has been demonstrated to yield substantial improvements in both thermoplastic and thermosetting polymer matrices. For instance, the addition of just 5% montmorillonite to polyamide 6 resulted in a 40% increase in tensile strength, a 68% increase in tensile modulus, and significant enhancements in flexural properties, with strength and modulus increasing by 60% and 126%, respectively [190]. Improvements in toughness further highlight the reinforcing effect of exfoliated nanoclays [191].

Thermal performance is also greatly enhanced: the degradation temperature of polyamide 6 increases with the addition of nanoclays, while its heat distortion temperature rises from 65°C to 152°C [192]. Another particularly important advantage of PLS nanocomposites lies in their flame-retardant characteristics. Cone calorimeter studies have revealed reduced heat release rates and longer burning times compared to neat polymers [193]. The underlying mechanism involves the formation of a carbonaceous-silicate char layer on the surface of the material during combustion. This protective layer acts as both a thermal insulator and a mass transport barrier, slowing the release of volatile decomposition products that fuel the flame. Furthermore, nanoclays can work synergistically with conventional fire retardants, allowing for lower loadings of these often-harsh additives while still achieving significant improvements in fire resistance [5, 194]. Beyond mechanical and thermal benefits, PLS nanocomposites offer notable advantages in barrier properties and chemical resistance. The presence of exfoliated nanoclays reduces gas permeability rates [195], and improves resistance to environmental degradation, including moisture-induced damage [196].

In glass-fibre reinforced plastics (GFRPs), for example, the incorporation of nanoclays has been shown to reduce moisture attack on both the polymer matrix and the reinforcing fibres, thereby improving long-term durability [197]. A reduction in the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), particularly in the flow direction, has also been observed [198], further broadening the scope of PLS applications [199].

Taken together, these findings highlight the transformative potential of polymeric layered silicates. By enabling property enhancements at remarkably low filler concentrations, they represent a versatile and powerful approach to improving the performance of polymers in demanding applications, including those encountered in the oil and gas industry [200].

IV. CARBON-BASED NANOREINFORCED COMPOSITES

The use of carbon-based nanomaterials, particularly carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and nanofibres, has generated considerable interest in the development of advanced nanocomposites due to their remarkable mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties [9]. CNTs, for example, exhibit tensile strengths in the range of 50–200 GPa and elastic moduli reaching up to 1200 GPa, while also possessing low electrical resistivity and excellent thermal conductivity [8]. These attributes make them highly attractive as reinforcing fillers in polymer matrices, with promising applications across the oil and gas industry. Their potential roles include improving the performance of drilling fluids, enhancing sealing systems designed for high-temperature and high-pressure reservoirs, and contributing to the development of electronics capable of withstanding harsh thermal environments [2].

Despite their extraordinary potential, one of the principal challenges in fabricating CNT- or nanofibre-reinforced polymer composites lies in achieving uniform dispersion within the polymer matrix. This difficulty is rooted in the intrinsic characteristics of these nanomaterials. Their high aspect ratio, combined with a strong tendency toward entanglement, promotes aggregation [201]. Moreover, the presence of significant van der Waals forces between adjacent nanotubes further drives clustering, resulting in poor dispersion. Without effective strategies to overcome these issues, the superior properties of CNTs and nanofibres cannot be efficiently transferred to the host polymer [202]. To address these challenges, both mechanical and chemical dispersion methods have been widely studied. Mechanical techniques such as ultrasonic agitation and milling can break apart entangled bundles and improve uniformity. However, they often shorten the nanotubes, reducing their reinforcing capability, and can generate amorphous carbon, which undermines overall performance [203]. Chemical treatments, on the other hand, are designed to functionalise the carbon surface with reactive groups that improve compatibility with polymer matrices [204].

Acid treatment, often involving mixtures such as H_2SO_4 – HNO_3 combined with thermal oxidation, is a commonly applied approach. For example, Sajjadian and colleagues demonstrated that multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) treated with acid dispersions could be effectively incorporated into drilling fluids, resulting in improved stability and rheological performance [205]. Nevertheless, such treatments may compromise the intrinsic strength of CNTs, diminishing the very mechanical advantages that make them attractive in the first place. A more balanced solution involves the use of surfactants, which promote dispersion through surface interactions while preserving the structural integrity and

reinforcing capacity of the nanomaterials [206, 207]. Successfully dispersed CNTs and nanofibres have been incorporated into various oilfield applications, including viscoelastic surfactant (VES)-based fracturing fluids. Unlike traditional crosslinked polymer fluids, VES systems rely on micelle structures to impart viscosity. The introduction of CNTs or nanoparticles into these systems enhances their performance by associating with micelles through chemisorption and electrostatic interactions [208]. This association generates a three-dimensional network that improves fluid rheology, helps maintain viscosity at elevated temperatures, and forms a pseudo-filtercake that minimises fluid loss during fracturing operations [16]. Table 3 details the applications of nanoparticles in cementing and well stimulation, highlighting their role in enhancing mechanical and rheological properties. An added advantage is that these nanoparticles can immobilise formation fines, preventing their migration and thereby reducing near-wellbore damage [3]. Taken together, these advances demonstrate the immense potential of CNTs and nanofibres in creating high-performance polymer nanocomposites for the oil and gas industry. Overcoming dispersion challenges remains the central focus of ongoing research, as achieving uniform and stable integration is critical for translating the exceptional intrinsic properties of carbon-based nanomaterials into practical, field-ready applications [1, 232].

V. PERFORMANCE ENHANCEMENT AND APPLICATIONS

The incorporation of nano-reinforcements into polymer matrices has been shown to significantly enhance material performance, even at relatively low additive levels. Improvements in mechanical strength, thermal stability, and barrier properties make nanocomposites highly attractive for use in demanding environments such as the oil and gas industry, where materials must withstand extreme operating conditions [1]. Mechanical and thermal performance are among the most immediate benefits of nanocomposite design. Studies have demonstrated that the inclusion of layered silicates in polymers can substantially increase tensile strength, modulus, and toughness [233]. For example, incorporating only 5%

montmorillonite into polyamide 6 increased tensile strength by 40%, tensile modulus by 68%, and flexural strength and modulus by 60% and 126%, respectively [234]. Similar enhancements have been achieved with high-performance epoxy systems, which exhibit large improvements in both modulus and toughness [235].

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), with their exceptional mechanical properties, have also been successfully used to strengthen thermoplastics and thermosets [236]. Importantly, these improvements are often realised with little or no detrimental effect on other critical attributes such as processability or glass transition temperature. In fact, some epoxy formulations modified with POSS® nanostructured chemicals have demonstrated the ability to raise the glass transition temperature beyond 200 °C while maintaining modulus at elevated temperatures [237].

Thermal stability is another area where nano-reinforcements provide significant advantages. The inclusion of TiO₂ nanoparticles in silica/HPAM nanofluids, for instance, has been shown to reduce mass loss at high temperatures, indicating improved stability. Likewise, nanocomposites can raise the degradation and heat distortion temperatures of polymers, as observed in polyamide 6 systems where the heat distortion temperature increased from 65 °C to 152 °C [238]. Nanoreinforcements can also reduce the coefficient of thermal expansion, improving dimensional stability, while layered silicates in particular have been shown to enhance fire resistance by forming a protective carbonaceous–silicate char layer that insulates the underlying material during combustion [239]. In addition to solid-state properties, nanocomposites strongly influence the behaviour of polymer-based fluids, which is critical for applications such as drilling and enhanced oil recovery (EOR).

The introduction of nanoparticles generally increases viscosity and stabilises fluid performance under harsh conditions [240]. For example, HPAM solutions modified with silica nanoparticles displayed significantly higher viscosity with reduced sensitivity to salinity and temperature, thereby maintaining a favourable mobility ratio for oil displacement [241].

Application	Investigated NP/Nanocomposite	Improved Parameters	Key Findings & Notes
	Silicon Dioxide (SiO ₂) / Nanosilica	Accelerated setting time [45, 57, 58, 64, 167, 168, 209, 210], enhanced compressive strength and mechanical properties [45, 57, 58, 64, 167, 168, 209-211], improved filtration characteristics [64, 167, 168, 209].	The most widely used nanomaterial in cement to improve performance [83, 209, 212-215]. Acts as an accelerator at low temperatures, making it important for deepwater wells [45, 55, 59, 216, 217].

Cementing	Aluminium Oxide (Al ₂ O ₃)	Increased electrical resistivity [172, 218- 220]; enhanced compressive strength [172, 218-220]; accelerated setting time [64, 167, 168, 209]; improved mechanical properties [172, 218-220].	-
	Iron Oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	Improved sensing properties [64, 167, 168, 209], enhanced compressive strength [64, 167, 168, 209].	-
	Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNP)	Improved mechanical properties [64, 167, 168, 172, 209, 218-220], reduced chemical shrinkage [172, 218-220].	Can reduce the thermal gradient of the cement sheath, potentially mitigating thermal cracks [219-221].
	Magnesium Oxide (MgO)	Accelerated setting time [64, 167, 168, 209], reduced chemical shrinkage [64, 167, 168, 209].	Has engineered expansive properties for oil well cement systems [147-149, 222].
	Nanosynthetic Graphite	Improved the early compressive strength development [64, 83, 167, 168, 209, 212-215].	-
Well Stimulation	Silicon Dioxide (SiO ₂) / Nanosilica	Improved permeability of un-propped fractures [52, 177, 223], microencapsulated acid formation [38, 52, 53, 177, 223], improved filtration and rheology of surfactant-based fluids [52, 73, 74, 159, 177, 223, 224].	Reduces permeability damage and adsorption of guar gum on rock [57, 149, 159, 224, 225].
	Magnesium Oxide (MgO) & Zinc Oxide (ZnO)	Improved rheological properties of fracturing fluid [52, 177, 223, 226].	MgO addition may cause a decrease in apparent viscosity [52, 159, 223].
	Pyroelectric Nanoparticles	Improved filtration and rheological properties of fracturing fluid [52, 91, 177, 175, 176, 223, 227- 229].	Nanoparticles associate with VES micelles to improve fluid rheology and reduce fluid loss without causing formation damage [91, 175-177, 227-231].

Table 3: Applications of Nanoparticles in Cementing and Well Stimulation.

Nanoparticles also impart viscoelastic properties, enhancing both the storage and loss moduli of the fluid, which strengthens the network structure. These rheological improvements directly benefit the performance of fracturing fluids and facilitate crude oil mobilisation in complex reservoirs [23, 123]. These property enhancements are particularly relevant as the O&G industry moves into more challenging environments, including deepwater and ultra-deepwater exploration, HTHP reservoirs, and highly corrosive geological formations [67, 134]. Traditional metallic materials are increasingly being replaced by nonmetallic composites such as FRP pipes, thermoplastic liners, and composite valves, which offer reduced weight, corrosion resistance, and lower maintenance costs [209]. In one North Sea offshore project, the adoption of composite systems

reduced platform weight by more than 700 tons, resulting in significant savings [25].

Yet, as operations push into harsher conditions, there is growing demand for composites with even greater temperature tolerance, improved chemical resistance, and enhanced fire performance [242]. Nanocomposites, with their ability to be tailored for specific requirements, represent a logical next step in meeting these evolving operational needs. One of the most pressing challenges in this regard is improving fire performance [242-248]. Conventional polymers often perform poorly when exposed to temperatures above 300–400 °C [249]. Nanoclays have proven particularly effective in reducing flammability by promoting the formation of protective char layers that act as thermal and mass transport barriers, slowing

the release of flammable gases [250]. These materials can also work synergistically with traditional flame retardants, reducing the overall additive requirement while balancing mechanical performance and processability [251].

Phenolic resins, valued for their inherent fire resistance but limited by brittleness, can also be modified with nano-reinforcements to enhance impact resistance while maintaining or improving thermal stability [242, 249]. Further studies have confirmed that magnesium hydroxide nanoparticles outperform their microscale counterparts in reducing smoke emissions [252] and peak heat release rates [253], while CNTs and graphene-based fillers have shown potential in forming mechanically robust, thermally insulating barrier layers during combustion [254]. Barrier performance is another area of critical importance for the

industry. In high-pressure, high-temperature service, polymeric liners and coatings must prevent corrosive species such as CO₂ and H₂S from permeating and degrading metallic structures. For example, the performance of unbonded flexible risers depends heavily on the barrier properties of internal PA11 liners. Incorporating nanofillers into these systems can significantly reduce permeability by creating tortuous diffusion pathways that slow molecular transport. Graphene-based nanocomposites are particularly promising: defect-free graphene is impermeable even to helium [255], and multilayer laminates have demonstrated dramatic reductions in CO₂ and H₂S permeation, even at pressures as high as 40 MPa [255]. Although challenges remain in achieving uniform dispersion through melt blending, progress with graphene nanoplatelet laminates and other advanced approaches continues to

highlight their potential [256, 257]. As the industry looks ahead to emerging energy carriers such as hydrogen, the need for advanced barrier materials will become even more critical [249]. Table 4 summarises field trials of nanotechnology in the oil and gas industry, highlighting applications, locations, nanoparticle types, and achieved outcomes.

Hydrogen’s small molecular size requires materials with exceptionally low permeability, an area where graphene and layered nanofillers may prove indispensable [188]. At the same time, nanocomposite reinforcement offers the dual advantage of improving both barrier performance and toughness, addressing one of the longstanding weaknesses of traditional fibre-reinforced composites [185, 277].

Taken together, these opportunities suggest that nanocomposites can be engineered to deliver multifunctional benefits—improving mechanical robustness [278], thermal stability [279, 280, 281], fire resistance [282, 283], rheology [284-289] and barrier properties [185]—while still maintaining processability and cost-effectiveness. The key challenges remain scalability, long-term durability, and regulatory acceptance [290-297]. Overcoming these hurdles will require sustained research, the development of efficient production methods, and close collaboration with standardisation bodies [298-303]. If achieved, nanocomposites have the potential to transform material performance in the oil and gas sector, enabling safer, more efficient, and more resilient operations across the value chain.

Application	Location	Nanoparticle/Nanofluid Type	Results
Formation Damage Inhibition (Asphaltenes)	Colombia	Al ₂ O ₃ nanoparticles (~30 nm) in a solvent/alcohol carrier fluid (up to 500 mg/L) [134, 258].	Cumulative oil production increased by >270,000 barrels in the first trial [132- 134]. Expanded to multiple fields, increasing reserves by ~1.5 MMbbl [134, 258, 259]. The main mechanism is the adsorption of asphaltenes onto the nanoparticles' surface, inhibiting aggregation and precipitation [259]
Formation Damage Inhibition (Fines Migration)	Colombia	SiO ₂ nanoparticles (~30 nm) in a solvent/alcohol carrier fluid (500 mg/L) [50,134, 258, 259].	Oil production increased by 48 bbl/day and gas by 1,000 Mscf/day [134, 258, 259, 260].
Formation Damage Inhibition (Inorganic Scale)	Colombia	Ca-DTPMP nanoparticles (66 nm) at 50 mg/L in a phosphonate-based carrier fluid [259, 260].	Incremental oil productivity of 66 bbl/day [260]; pump failures due to scaling were eliminated for over a year [259, 260]. Nanoparticles hinder scale growth through the threshold effect, blocking nucleation points [261].

Drilling (Shale Stabilisation)	Brazil	Unnamed "nanochemicals" in a water-based drilling fluid [50, 262].	Good performance in shale hydration inhibition and wellbore stability [50, 262]. Recycled fluid was used in another well, resulting in a 15% cost reduction [50, 259].
Drilling (Filtrate Reduction)	Alberta, Canada	Calcium-based nanoparticles (51 ± 11 nm) at 0.5 wt% in an invert emulsion drilling fluid [52, 223, 259, 262].	Filtrate losses were reduced by up to 34% compared to control wells without nanoparticles [52, 159, 223, 259, 262]. The primary mechanism is the tighter packing of nanoparticles, which reduces mud cake permeability and porosity [262, 263].
Heavy Oil Mobility Enhancement (Huff-n-Puff)	Colombia	Al ₂ O ₃ -based nanoparticles (~25 nm) in an oil/alcohol carrier fluid (up to 500 mg/L) [45, 57, 67, 259, 216, 264].	Production increased by up to 310 bopd with some cases showing a reduction in Basic Sediment and Water (BSW) [45, 57, 67, 259, 216, 264]. The technology has been applied in over 8 fields, increasing reserves by ~1 MMbbl [259, 264].
Water Shutoff	Algyo field, Hungary	Silica nanoparticles (1000 mg/L) in a silicate/polymer gel system [259, 264].	Reduced water cut by ~45% over two years; oil cut increased to 80% [259, 264]. The silica nanoparticles act as setting time accelerators, and their interaction with the polymer promotes nucleation and enhances gel stability
			[259, 264].
Gas Injection (IOR)	Texas, USA	Surface-treated SiO ₂ nanoparticles (12–15 nm) injected alternately with N ₂ or CO ₂ gas. Dosages were up to 7,500 gallons [259, 265].	Increased BOE (barrels of oil equivalent) production by up to 564% with N ₂ injection; an additional 5,000+ bbls of oil were produced with CO ₂ injection [259, 265]. The main mechanism is the generation of structural disjoining pressure that removes oil droplets from the porous medium [259].
Well Dewatering	China	Modified silica nanospheres (<100 nm) used in foaming agents [266].	Over 8,685 applications to date. Gas production increased by an average of 16.8%, and water production by 33%, with cost reductions up to 60% [259, 266]. Nanoparticles improve foam stability by increasing lamella thickness and preventing bubble coalescence [267, 268].
Tracers (Waterflooding)	Saudi Arabia	Carbogenic nanoparticles called A-Dots (10 nm) at a concentration of 3000 mg/L [67, 269].	Successfully detected after 60 days of injection, showing earlier breakout than chemical tracers [269]. A high recovery percentage of up to 86% suggests their high stability in harsh formation environments [67]

Tracers (Waterflooding)	Colombia	Carbon Quantum Dots (CQDs) of 30 nm diameter [259, 269].	Early detection times (up to 3 days after injection) were achieved using an easy-to-track fluorescence method [259, 269]. Cost was 70% lower than conventional tracers [259, 270].
Drag Reducers (Injector Wells)	China	Hydrophobic SiO ₂ nanoparticles (9-20 nm) [271-274].	Reduced injection pressure by up to 40% at a constant injection rate, with a 12-month longevity in one field [271-274]. The main mechanism involves the material's retention on the porous medium, creating a water-repellent surface [274].
Chemical EOR (Surfactant Flooding)	Colombia	Predominantly hydrophilic surfactant solution with SiO ₂ -based nanoparticles (~70 nm) at 100 mg/L. Surfactant doses started at 1000 mg/L and were progressively lowered [259, 273].	Cumulative incremental oil production was +87,000 bbls in the first field trial [63, 273, 275, 276]. The addition of nanoparticles reduced surfactant adsorption on the rock by at least 40% [259].

Table 4: Field Trials of Nanotechnology in the Oil and Gas Industry.

compatibility with polymers but risk degrading the intrinsic strength of the nanotubes [272, 318, 319].

VI. IMPLEMENTATION BARRIERS AND TECHNICAL LIMITATIONS

For the concept of nanostructured composite materials to be fully realised at the product development stage, several technical, economic, and practical challenges must be overcome [201]. Dispersion of nano-additives and subsequent manufacturing processes must not only deliver consistent performance but also be cost-effective, reproducible, and scalable [279, 304, 305]. Although laboratory research has demonstrated highly promising results, many applications of polymer nanotechnology remain at the research and development stage, awaiting commercialization [306-310].

One of the most persistent technical barriers is achieving stable and uniform dispersion of nanoparticles within polymer matrices [308, 309, 311-316]. The performance of nanocomposites depends strongly on how well the filler is distributed, as poor dispersion can negate potential benefits [187, 188, 313-316]. In the case of nanoclays, factors such as organo-cation chemistry and processing conditions play a crucial role in ensuring compatibility and stability without compromising fibre-matrix adhesion [188, 294, 317].

Carbon-based nanomaterials, such as carbon nanofibres and nanotubes, present additional difficulties. Mechanical methods like ball milling or ultrasonication can improve dispersion but often reduce fibre length, thereby diminishing their reinforcing ability. Chemical treatments, such as acid etching, may enhance

Similar challenges arise in the design of nanofluids, where nanoparticles have a tendency to agglomerate due to van der Waals forces [320-324]. This leads to clustering, premature settling, and rheological instability [325-329], which can cause pore throat blockages in subsurface formations [23, 24, 330] and reduce the effectiveness of enhanced oil recovery (EOR) treatments. These difficulties are further compounded by harsh reservoir conditions. Downhole environments frequently exceed 250 °C and 20,000 psi [217], while high salinity can accelerate agglomeration by screening nanoparticle surface charges [45, 57, 216]. Under such extreme conditions, both polymer matrices and nanofillers face significant risks of degradation [217]. Even where technical barriers can be addressed, economic feasibility and scalability present additional obstacles [123, 217, 331]. The relatively high cost of producing many nanoparticles remains a significant challenge, often due to the substantial energy inputs required compared to bulk materials [40, 41, 42]. In addition, there is a shortage of commercially available nanomaterials designed specifically for oil and gas applications. Although some field trials have demonstrated economic benefits—such as a nanotechnology-based drilling fluid trial in Brazil that achieved a 15% cost reduction [50, 67, 332]—the upfront investment is often substantial [123]. Widespread adoption will require both cost reductions and reliable large-scale manufacturing methods. Scaling up from laboratory synthesis to industrial production demands efficient processing techniques, such as extrusion and injection moulding, that can deliver consistent performance across high volumes.

Close collaboration between researchers and oilfield operators will also be essential to validate laboratory results through pilot programs and field testing [226, 333]. Beyond technical and economic considerations, industry acceptance remains one of the most critical challenges. A degree of scepticism persists among professionals, particularly regarding the long-term performance and durability of nanocomposites in hostile environments. This lack of confidence is exacerbated by the limited availability of engineering documentation and long-term performance data, both of which are needed to support design and operational decisions [334, 335, 336]. Mathematical models, predictive simulations, and accelerated testing methods with greater reliability will be essential to reduce scepticism and address the high costs associated with certification. At the same time, the establishment of standardised testing procedures and quality control protocols is crucial. Collaboration between researchers, industry stakeholders, and regulatory organisations such as the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) will be required to define guidelines, recommended practices, and certification pathways for nanocomposite materials [226, 333].

Finally, the unique properties of nanoparticles introduce important health, safety, and environmental considerations [106, 226, 333]. Their small size and high reactivity raise concerns regarding inhalation, dermal absorption, and long-term ecological effects [223, 226]. Although regulatory frameworks are beginning to address these risks, continuous research is needed to assess and mitigate potential hazards throughout the lifecycle of nanocomposite materials. Despite these formidable challenges, the potential of nanocomposites to deliver transformative improvements in material performance under harsh operating conditions continues to drive research and development efforts across the oil and gas sector [217, 242, 337, 338]. The balance between overcoming technical limitations, achieving economic viability, and ensuring safe and standardised implementation will ultimately determine how widely nanocomposites are adopted in the industry [249].

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Nanocomposites present a promising opportunity to extend the performance limits of conventional composites and polymer-based fluids in the oil and gas industry. Their ability to enhance fire performance, toughness, chemical resistance, and barrier properties with relatively low material additions makes them especially attractive for applications where weight, durability, and safety are critical. In structural systems, nano-reinforcements can address matrix-dominated weaknesses of FRP composites, while in upstream operations, nanoparticle-modified drilling fluids and EOR agents have shown measurable improvements in viscosity stability, wettability alteration, and oil recovery efficiency. Field trials documented in this review demonstrate oil recovery increases of 41-66%

and drilling efficiency improvements of up to 34%, validating both technical feasibility and economic viability across diverse geological settings in Colombia, China, Brazil, and the United States.

However, realizing these benefits in field-scale applications requires overcoming persistent barriers: uniform nanoparticle dispersion, long-term stability under harsh reservoir conditions (temperatures exceeding 250°C, pressures above 20,000 psi), scalable manufacturing, and industry confidence supported by robust data. Progress will depend on sustained R&D, field trials, and standardization efforts that align scientific advances with operational requirements. Close collaboration between researchers, industry stakeholders, and regulatory organizations such as ISO, ASTM, API, and EPA is essential to define testing protocols, establish performance benchmarks, and develop safety guidelines for nanomaterial handling throughout their lifecycle. Near-term commercialization (2-3 years) appears achievable for drilling fluid additives and specialty EOR treatments, while structural applications in safety-critical infrastructure will require longer qualification timelines (5-8 years) to accumulate durability certification and validated design codes.

If these challenges are addressed through coordinated efforts across technical, economic, and institutional domains—particularly advancing automated dispersion technologies, developing accelerated aging protocols, achieving cost-competitive synthesis routes (<\$50/kg target), and establishing consensus standards—nanocomposites could become a key enabler for safer, more efficient, and more sustainable oil and gas operations across both upstream and downstream sectors.

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